

THE USE OF PARALINGUISTIC DEVICES IN LITERARY WORKS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Dehqonboyeva Madina

The researcher of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

madinadehqonboyeva01gmail.com

Tel: +99890 688 82 08

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Abstract. In this thesis, the employment of paralinguistic strategies in English and Uzbek literary works is analyzed. Non-verbal tools of communication, such as body language, gestures, intonation, facial emotions, pauses, tone and others enhances spoken language by adding additional components of communications and in some situations they are dominant to convey message to an addressant. These devices in literary texts guarantee that characters' speech is natural and represent their social standing, psychological condition, and national identity. For example, in "Utkan Kunlar", a novel by Abdulla Qodiriy, the characters' speech pauses and tone reveal their inner feelings, whereas in Utkir Hoshimov's works, the characters' personalities are vividly depicted through the descriptions of their facial expressions and movements. The dramatic power of pauses and intonation is emphasised in William Shakespeare's plays shows how gestures help to depict characters.

Introduction. When we think about communication, we most often focus on how we exchange information using words. While verbal communication is essential, humans relied on nonverbal communication for thousands of years before we developed the capability to communicate with words. It is written in the book "A Primer on communication studies" that nonverbal communication is a process of generating meaning using behavior other than words. Rather than thinking of nonverbal communication as the opposite of or as separate from verbal communication, it's more accurate to view them as operating side by side - as part of the same system. Yet, as part of the same system, they still have important differences, including how the brain processes them¹.

In recent decades, the study of paralinguistic qualities has drawn a lot of interest in linguistics and literary criticism since they are a crucial component of communication that goes beyond the spoken language. A vast array of expressive techniques, including intonation, stress, pauses, facial expressions, gestures, and body movements, are considered paralinguistic devices. These techniques enhance spoken language and add more interpretive depth. Because paralinguistics serves as "the bridge between language and non-verbal communication," academics like David Crystal stress that it is essential to the study of literary discourse².

Paralinguistic devices are useful techniques that expose characters' inner lives, provide dramatic tension, and reflect the sociocultural environment of communication in literature. They are not only stylistic embellishments. For example, depictions of imitation and informal gestures are abundant in Uzbek literary works, emphasising the characters' cultural identity. In contrast, English literature frequently uses paralinguistic devices to heighten dramatic effect, as shown in Charles Dickens' books and William Shakespeare's plays. Paralinguistic devices are useful techniques that expose characters' inner lives, provide dramatic tension, and reflect the

¹ A Primer on communication studies. Creative Commons books, 2012. Chapter 4, 181 p.

² David Crystal. Paralanguage, Cambridge University Press, 1969, p. 12

sociocultural environment of communication in literature. They are not only stylistic embellishments. For example, depictions of imitation and informal gestures are abundant in Uzbek literary works, emphasising the characters' cultural identity. In contrast, English literature frequently uses paralinguistic devices to heighten dramatic effect, as shown in Charles Dickens' books and William Shakespeare's plays.

Discussion and results. Paralanguage plays a crucial role in literary discourse by enriching character speech and enhancing reader perception. They often serve to reveal hidden emotions, intensify dramatic effect, and add cultural specificity to dialogues.

If we start with Uzbek literary works, we can identify that non-verbal devices are great tools to convey the meaning of nation's identity by expressing of emotions including shyness, pure love, silence, bravery and confidence. For example, in Abdulla Qodiriy's *Utkan kunlar*, the author frequently employs pauses and intonational markers to illustrate inner hesitation or emotional turmoil:

*"... Kumushning ko'zlari yoshlanib, u jim qoldi..."*³.

Here, the silence ("jim qoldi") functions as a paralinguistic marker expressing sorrow and suppressed feelings. Similarly, in Utkir Hoshimov's "Dunyoning ishlari", gestures and facial expressions are meticulously described to describe the pure emotions of mother:

*"...Onaning yuzida charchoq tabassum paydo bo'ldi..."*⁴

Here "tired smile" conveys both endurance and unspoken pain, showing how paralinguistic detail strengthens the psychological portrait of the character.

Another invaluable literature work in paralinguistics is Tahir Malik's "Shaytanat" which is very artistically rich, depicting important situations not only with words, but also with the help of paralinguistic devices. These devices serve to enhance the characters' inner feelings, mood, and the drama of the situation:

"... Mening paytavamga emas, sening miyangga qurt tushgan, - Asadbek shunday deb Qamarga qarab qo'ydi. U erkaklar gaplashayotganda ayol kishining atrofda ivirsib yurishini yoqtirmas edi. Qamar Asadbekning maqsadini anglab tezgina chiqib ketdi..."

Here, the meaning of the gaze that Asadbek did to Qamar expresses she should go out because he doesn't like women's disturbance when males are talking. Therefore, she silently went out by showing respect to him and situation.

When a person enters into a conversation, he uses not only the lungs, pharynx, oral cavity, tongue, teeth, lips, which make up the speech apparatus, but also the eyes, eyebrows, face, nose, hands, feet and other body parts. Linguistic and paralinguistic means are, in fact, complementary practical opportunities. The extent to which they are used depends on the person's life experience, knowledge and skills, and manners. In the novel "Kecha va kunduz" by Chulpon, we can analyze characters' manner:

"...— Enaxonni bilasiz-a? Yoyilma soydagi o'rtogim bor-ku?"

Zebi boshini ko'tarib, o'rtog'iga qaradi, shu qarash nechikdir Enaxonni eslolmay turganini ko'rsatardi. Sungra Salti ta'rif qildi:

³ Abdulla Qodiriy. *O'tkan kunlar*. -T: Sharq, 2010, p.89

⁴ O'tkir Hoshimov, *Dunyoning ishlari*, Toshkent: Sharq, 2010, p. 89

— *O'tgan kuz biznikiga mehmon bo'lib kelishdi-ku — kelinibisi bilan birga? O'shanda necha marta odam yuborib chaqirtirdim, bormadingiz, otangiz javob bermadi... Zebi bosh tebratdi:*

— *Ha, ha... bildim, bildim. O'zini ko'rganim yo'q-ku, eshitib bilaman."*

Zebi's "looking up" to Salti's first question is a nonverbal response, while her "nodding" to the second is an example of the parallel use of verbal and nonverbal means.

In English literature, narrative and dramatic frameworks frequently incorporate paralinguistic elements. William Shakespeare frequently employs stage instructions and pauses to increase the intensity of the emotions. Hesitation is shown in Hamlet through silence and broken speech:

"...The question is, to be or not to be."⁵

This pause highlights Hamlet's internal struggle and heightens the soliloquy's philosophical impact. In a similar way, Charles Dickens regularly uses gesture to highlight character features in his speech. He explains Mr. Bumble's expressive body language in *Oliver Twist*:

"Mr. Bumble raised his chin in arrogant resistance As a paralinguistic indicator of personality and social standing, the gesture of "lifting the chin" conveys conceit and pride.

If we compare both Uzbek and English literature, in Uzbek novels paralinguistic markers are dominant in reflecting cultural intimacy and everyday realism whereas dramatic intensity and emotional resonance are amplified in English literature. In spite of these differences, paralinguistic features contribute dialogue authenticity, shape character identity and guide reader interpretation in both traditions.

Conclusion. The artistic and communicative richness of literature is demonstrated by the comparative study of paralinguistic devices in English and Uzbek literary works. Intonation, pauses, gestures, and facial expressions are examples of paralinguistic aspects that are used in both traditions to represent cultural communication norms, enhance conversation authenticity, and convey characters' innermost feelings. The oral narrative style and national attitude are closely associated with paralinguistic descriptions in Uzbek literature. Both the weary smile in O'tkir Hoshimov's *Dunyoning ishlari* and the quiet of Kumush in Abdulla Qodiriy's *O'tkan kunlar* represent culturally grounded manifestations of emotional reserve, endurance, and modesty. These subtleties reflect the communicative culture of the Uzbek people, where nonverbal cues and indirectness have profound social significance.

English literature, on the other hand, especially that of William Shakespeare, frequently employs paralinguistic techniques to emphasise individuality and heighten dramatic action. The expressive, performance-oriented nature of English narrative tradition is shown in the purposeful pauses in Hamlet and the prideful gestures in *Oliver Twist*, which highlight emotional strain and social identity. In the end, the research shows that paralinguistic traits are influenced by many linguistic and cultural systems even if they serve a common purpose. By connecting the explicit and implicit, as well as the verbal and nonverbal, they enhance the interpretive aspect of literature. As a result, this study advances our knowledge of the ways in

⁵ William Shakespeare, *Hamlet*. London: Arden Shakespeare, 2006, p. 102.

which language, culture, and emotion interact in creative discourse and confirms that literary communication transcends the use of words.

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